

Large language models, neuro-symbolic AI and first-order logic: Musings from a knowledge representation viewpoint

Vaishak Belle,
University of Edinburgh, UK
vbelle@ed.ac.uk

June 21, 2023

Abstract

In this article, we informally review logical reasoning abilities of large language models, and how that seems to suggest that these models are neither deep thinkers nor an existential threat, in the sense of a rogue autonomous agent. Sample conversations are included to illustrate its shallowness. Its impact on democracy and our sanity by way of misinformation is another matter, of course. We conclude by arguing for the need to revert to well-established areas that unify logic and learning, such as statistical relational learning and neuro-symbolic AI, which enable frameworks for clear behavior specification. We note, nonetheless, that these frameworks are yet to embrace full first-order logical features, which could be an exciting avenue for future research.

1 Overview

There are many areas of overlap between language, logic, and learning. Naturally, then, with the recent prominence of chatbots powered by large language models, there is quite a lot of chatter in terms of how much these models impact the fundamental science of artificial intelligence. For instance, is it the case that they will lead to new models of language acquisition and linguistic reasoning? What kind of logical and mathematical capabilities will they have? It is important to note that the basic architecture seems most equipped to pick up on statistical correlations by predicting the subsequent word based on a previous set of words. Given that some of the responses reported on social media are cogent and creative, all of the above are extremely pertinent questions.

Of course, it is impossible to predict how this technology will evolve in the coming years, but our informal review of the logical reasoning abilities of large language models seems to suggest that these models are neither deep thinkers nor an existential threat, in the sense of a rogue autonomous agent. Its impact on democracy, privacy, and our sanity by way of misinformation is another matter, of course.

We then argue for the need to revert to well-established areas that unify logic and learning, such as statistical relational learning and neuro-symbolic AI. We discuss the philosophical and logical foundations of these approaches and point out that they are still lacking in fully embracing first-order logical features.

2 Large-language models seem impressive

A few weeks ago, Geoff Hinton, Turing-award winner and long-term advocate for using neural networks for artificial general intelligence, quit Google to talk about AI risks [39]. His concern is centered around so-

called Large Language Models (LLMs) and Chatbots that use that technology [21]: the most representative example being OpenAI's chatGPT. In simple terms, the models predict the next word by utilizing stochastic associations and a hint of randomness to lend creativity to the prediction. What makes them particularly noteworthy, compared to most language models from, say, even late as 2016, is that their particular attention mechanism. This is enabled via the so-called "transformer" architecture [70], which allows them to keep track of the context for, say, a 100 or even a 1000 words, thereby making the next predicted word a very good suggestion (from a probability viewpoint). This makes them so powerful that they can, say, summarise a paragraph such as the one I just wrote (or even a paper), rephrase it in the style of, say, Shakespeare.

For example, here's what I get from when I ask for a summary of the above paragraph in at most 3 lines:

Geoff Hinton, a Turing-award winner and advocate for using neural networks for AGI, left Google to raise concerns about the risks associated with Large Language Models (LLMs) and Chatbots that use that technology, such as OpenAI's chatGPT. These models can predict the next word with high accuracy, making them very powerful and capable of summarizing complex texts or even rephrasing them in the style of famous writers.

And here's what I get when I ask for summary of at most 2 lines in the style of Shakespeare:

*A wizened scholar, Geoff Hinton by name,
Didst quit Google, to speak of AI's bane.
Concerns arose o'er Large Language Models bold,
And Chatbots too, whose tech doth not behold Thee and me, but rather stochastic might,
And randomness to lend them creative sight.
Yet more of worth - their focus on the clue
And context, which makes predictions anew,
A power so great they can summarise A paragraph in Shakespearean guise.*

The first summary might be passable, but the second should, at first glance, seem remarkable. Here's what I get when I ask the title of the article to be expanded in the style of Shakespeare:

Oh, harken ye all, and heed my warning clear, For existential risk doth loom quite near. Amidst the workings of logical thought, A tool hath grown both useful and fraught.

The large language model, its power vast, Doth aid our queries with great contrast. But dangerous it is, make no mistake, For its workings oft doth logic forsake.

Slightly useful in its capability, But the peril it brings is quite palpable, verily! For in the realm of existential threat, This tool may serve to bring much regret.

Think not its largesse doth bring us gain, For in its workings lies much disdain. The dangers are many, its faults astir, And caution must be had ere it we prefer.

With logical reasoning its power lies, Yet in its use our judgment oft dies. For though its vast capacity may seem grand, In heedless action it may bring destruction to the land.

So let us be wary, and hold fast to care, Lest in our using of this tool we dare To bring upon us dangers unawares, And make our existential threat, that much harder to repair.

Impressive still, perhaps, but it starts bordering on silly, and seems to re-use some rhyming strategy, at least when you contrast the two Shakespeare-style outputs.

3 Unpacking Hinton's worries

If you find these suggestions remarkable, you may also find the following points raised by Geoff Hinton to be aligned with your concerns [39]:

1. *Compare a pretrained large language model with a human in the speed of learning a task like that and the human's edge vanishes, he says.*

2. *The difference is that humans usually confabulate more or less correctly, says Hinton. To Hinton, making stuff up isn't the problem. Computers just need a bit more practice.*
3. *"Our brains have 100 trillion connections," says Hinton. "Large language models have up to half a trillion, a trillion at most. Yet GPT-4 knows hundreds of times more than any one person does. So maybe it's actually got a much better learning algorithm than us."*

Let us break down these concerns and examine them more closely. Firstly, there is the question of learning. It seems plausible to assume that computational platforms can learn at a much faster rate than humans. But even if that is true, there is a considerable debate in computational psychology about whether humans possess pre-existing structures that give us an advantage in learning [52]. For example, it is obvious that children do not need to see a thousand samples of the number "0" written in different styles for them to recognize it the next time they see it.

The second concern is regarding confabulation. It is important to understand that what is meant by confabulation in language models – obviously shamelessly borrowing the term of from human psychology at the peril of anthromorphising – is the act of making predictions without proper ground truth or accuracy [2]. This is akin to open world reasoning [7], but without an explicit open world model that determines the conditions under which an observed fact can be made up. As Rodney Brooks argues:¹

What the large language models are good at is saying what an answer should sound like, which is different from what an answer should be.

Indeed, an appropriate answer should be based on a proper understanding of the world model [59, 33]. So the confabulation is not simply a matter of practice: it is the question of a justified theory of the world (in the form of, say, an ontology [27]) advising predictions. This is sometimes referred to as "knowledge-enhanced" machine learning [29].

Finally, it is true that chatbots may have access to more information than humans. However, if the model is solely based on database retrieval, it cannot seriously be seen as an instance of "super" intelligence, let alone human intelligence. The philosopher David Chalmers has a larger laundry list of features that should, in the least, be expected from any intelligent entity said to have consciousness [23].

So LLMs are not there yet, and fears of super-intelligence and "alien-mind" are misplaced, at least in a common sense understanding [19], which necessitates a model of naive physics and naive psychology in the least. But this is not stopping excitement about its impact in everything from parasitology [66] to oncology [45].

4 Mostly dumb

But putting philosophical [23] and intuitive concerns [19] aside, surely, there is cause for alarm if the system is intelligent in ways we cannot fully fathom? Who is to say that Chalmers exhaustively identified all the indicator criteria? What about Walter Reuther's duck test: "If it looks like a duck, walks like a duck and quacks like a duck, then it just may be a duck"?

It is impossible to answer this question categorically: we do not yet have a formal theory of the internal and implicit model of LLMs, we can only understand and explicate its probabilistic mechanics. Whether such a mechanics is, unbeknownst to us, constructing a clever world model in a language and theory we do not understand, who can say?

¹<https://spectrum.ieee.org/gpt-4-calm-down>

But one thing we can do is check for some type of a reasoning capacity: after all, if we are feeding it enormous amounts of textual data that include, say, patterns of logical reasoning, and it trained to predict those patterns, can we not expect it to exhibit these? Logical reasoning [9] is usually studied in three flavours:

1. *Deduction*: from sentences $\alpha, \beta, \dots, \gamma$, if all permutations of truth assignments to these sentences also make true a sentence δ , then we write $\alpha \wedge \beta \wedge \dots \gamma \models \delta$. For example, if we know humans are mortal, and Bob is a human, then we conclude Bob is mortal too.
2. *Induction*: from sentences $\alpha(1), \alpha(2), \dots, \alpha(n)$, if we can identify a sub-formula (or pattern) $\beta(x)$ such that it describes every observation we make of the world, then we say $\beta(x)$ is an induced formula that captures the instances in $\alpha(x)$. For example, if we see that the parent of the parent of Bob is referred to as the grandparent of Bob, and likewise for Lisa, and so too for John, we can conclude that $\text{parent}(x, y) \wedge \text{parent}(y, z) \rightarrow \text{grandparent}(x, z)$.
3. *Abduction*: given sentence α and observation β , what must be the smallest assumption δ such that $\alpha \wedge \delta$ explain β ? This, of course, is the Sherlock Holmes strategy for solving cases, mistakenly referred to as deduction by Arthur Conan Doyle.

Although extensive analysis on such tasks is still ongoing [30, 73], anecdotal evidence (mainly on social media websites such as twitter) is indicating that, somewhat shockingly (if you compare against its attempt at Shakespeare), LLMs are mostly dumb.

For example, the Oxford philosopher Luciano Floridi asks²:

what's the name of the daughter of Laura's mother?

ChatGPT (even GPT-4, the latest and best comes back with) something to the effect of: "I'm sorry, I don't have personal information about specific individuals." The use of personal pronouns here is irresponsible [74], but that is a topic for another debate.

There are two ways to get it out its quagmire. Either you can prompt it by saying that "it is a logic test", or as I have done, explicate the question further to the point of sounding pedantic:³

Vaishak Belle — Laura's mother has one daughter. Laura is female. what's name of Laura's mother's daughter.

The name of Laura's mother's daughter is Laura.

Vaishak Belle — how many children does Laura's mother have

Laura's mother has one daughter, who is Laura.

Perhaps the error here is on our expectations. Maybe the correct thing indeed is provide a detailed context, before asking such a question. I will not provide other examples here, but very innocuous looking examples can throw the system seriously off.

Nevertheless, it does pick up the logic of the exercise, so when I continue with the following different individual, but without pedantic details:

Vaishak Belle — what's name of sara's mother's daughter.

If Sara's mother has a daughter, and assuming that Sara's mother has only one daughter, then the name of Sara's mother's daughter is Sara.

What about transitivity, as captured by the grandparent relationship I discussed above?

Vaishak Belle — Johnny is to John what George is to John. I'll call George the wazoo of John. Sara is to Mary what Katie is to Sara. I'll call Katie the wazoo of Sara. what do you understand from this.

²<https://twitter.com/Floridi/status/1635951391968567296?s=20>

³<https://twitter.com/vaishakbelle/status/1636114713057665024?s=20>

The sentences are using a word “wazoo” as a playful way of referring to the relationship between two people.

The first sentence is a comparison between the names “Johnny” and “John” and “George” and “John”. It suggests that “George” is to “John” as “Johnny” is to “John”. The term “wazoo” is introduced as a playful way to refer to this relationship.

Vaishak Belle — based on this, suppose mara is to Clara as Nicola is to mara. what’s the relationship between Nicola and clara

Based on the given statement, “Mara is to Clara as Nicola is to Mara,” we can use the term “wazoo” to describe the relationship between the names.

So, if we call Mara the wazoo of Clara, and Nicola the wazoo of Mara, we can say that Nicola is the wazoo of the wazoo of Clara.

Therefore, the relationship between Nicola and Clara is that Nicola is the grand-wazoo of Clara (i.e., the “wazoo” of the “wazoo” of Clara).

What about logical puzzles? The computer scientist Vincent Conitzer tried this out:⁴

I put one apple in a bag. Then I put either one pear or two bananas in the bag. Then I remove one piece of fruit. Then I remove all the remaining pieces of fruit from the bag. Based on what I told you, is it possible to know exactly how many pieces of fruit remain in the bag?

Based on the information provided, it is not possible to know exactly how many pieces of fruit remain in the bag after removing one piece of fruit and then removing all remaining pieces. This is because there are two possible scenarios, but we don’t have enough information to determine which one took place:

- 1. One apple and one pear were in the bag. If you removed one piece of fruit, there would be one piece left. After removing all remaining pieces, there would be 0 pieces left.*
- 2. One apple and two bananas were in the bag. If you removed one piece of fruit, there would be two pieces left. After removing all remaining pieces, there would also be 0 pieces left.*

In both scenarios, after removing one piece of fruit and then removing all remaining pieces, there are no pieces of fruit left in the bag.

Apparently in a follow-up reply to that tweet, GPT-4 seems to get it correct.⁵

What can we make of all of this? These models are clearly not reliable, or consistent [41]. Perhaps this what prompted Stephen Wolfram to consider a systematic integration of ChatGPT and Wolfram Alpha.⁶ Looking at the above examples, this is undoubtedly beneficial to OpenAI too.

There are, of course, plenty of other examples for integrating LLMs and other symbolic solvers, and this is an exciting area for the future of logic, as seen in neuro-symbolic AI [73] and for epistemic logic [65]. However, the “native” capabilities are clearly limited. An intriguing hypothesis put forward by eminent AI scientist Subbarao Kambhampati is this:⁷

I think many of the claims about LLM’s reasoning capabilities miss the point that LLM’s are not just trained on “facts” but also, quite often, the deductive closure of those facts. Thus reasoning becomes (approximate) retrieval.

If this is the case, these models do not reason at all, but simply see for patterns of conclusions, which might limit, say, the number of inference steps, or how involved the reasoning is. For example, can it solve Sudoku and other logical puzzles by retrieval [48]?

⁴<https://twitter.com/conitzer/status/1636156048347111425?s=20>

⁵<https://twitter.com/SebastienBubeck/status/1636251553349910530?s=20>

⁶<https://www.wolfram.com/wolfram-plugin-chatgpt/>

⁷<https://twitter.com/rao2z/status/1666294366720360449?s=20>

5 Slightly useful

As discussed earlier, none of these limitations are affecting the excitement about the impacts of LLMs, including in critical applications in medicine [66, 45]. Just as a simple exercise, a search on Google scholar for “large language models openAI” returns 30,000 research articles! This is not to say that they are all positively inclined toward this technology, but a cursory glance does seem to indicate that they largely are. And its a surprising to see this excitement, given that just a year ago, explainability was the hot topic [15], and there was vocal disdain for black box models [63].

If we put aside tricks about writing like Shakespeare and Bob Dylan, it is clearly useful for things like preparing a skeleton presentation from your previous paper or summarising a research paper. (These are the pitching points for the new Microsoft Copilot service as part of the Office 365 suite.) But if logical reasoning is any testbed at all, there are reasons to be cautious about its use in science [17].

How deeply problematic is it? Basically, as argued before, GPT models (by which we mean the architecture, training regime, and so on) lacks a strong foundational basis because it does not build an actual world model. It doesn’t understand that the world has objects and properties, that are further related at a macro and micro level, that somethings exist because of other things, and somethings cause other things. Sure, it might readily complete a sentence of the form: “rain causes the grass to be wet”, because this is a popular example used in AI textbooks. But it doesn’t understand what it is about rain that causes the grass to be wet, and what would happen to the part of the grass that is covered, say, by a tarp. (Unless such a thing was discussed somewhere, of course.) It may not know that acid rain not only causes the grass to get wet, but potentially destroy the fertile ground on which the grass grows. If it does get questions of this sort correct, we only have ourselves to congratulate because there are enough texts written by us for it to predict what the next word ought to be. That is, it does not work by predicting what the next word ought to be based on concepts and physics.

Of course, in the logic community, we are aware that there are approaches that attempt to capture human-level commonsense based on the notion of an ontology. The semantic web, for example, relies on this notion [56]. Therefore, with enough training data, interactive feedback from human users, suggestive prompts, and background knowledge in the form of one or more ontologies, the statistics-guided utterances produced by chatbots could become more meaningful. If chatbots are properly and systematically coupled with such ontologies, we may even suggest that there is indeed a world model, and the relationship between concepts in utterances is understood by the computer because it has worked out the “why” question. However, there is still lots of work to be done to get there, as the task of building a comprehensive commonsense knowledge base that captures causality, and micro and macro-level properties remains a grand challenge [19].

But until then, what we have are dumb models that can accidentally produce intriguing poems and essays through cross-pollinating (and, dare I say, cross-contaminating) sources. Much of this content is taken without the consent of artists and authors and put into practice without first getting consent from users. While these models might be able to automate some mundane tasks such as “check my essay for grammatical mistakes” and “summarize the last three paragraphs I wrote into a few lines because I went way over the word limit,” other mundane tasks like “expand my paragraph into three” would likely need to be checked for accuracy and plagiarism. They could either take from one of your sources without attribution or plagiarize from your previous work, mandating careful review. Consequently, these models will be of limited usefulness for true creativity and novelty, at best.

Just to provide a concrete example about how wild the confabulation can get, I asked about one of my favorite papers [5] – this is a first-order logical proposal for reasoning about degrees of beliefs and

probability in a dynamic setting.⁸ It seems to:

- make up the title of the paper and then apologise;
- make up the year it was published (1997 in reality vs 2005 as per chatGPT);
- mix the contributions of Mateus, Pinto and others [53] which introduces the PSC with the work of Bacchus et al;
- make a claim about theorems in the paper — there are none;
- claims that the regression result was proved in the paper, which is actually work that I co-authored [14].

Vaishak Belle - Explain the paper by Bacchus, Halpern and Levesque (1997)

The paper by Bacchus, Halpern, and Levesque, titled “Reasoning about Partially Observable Events,” presents a formalism for reasoning about partially observable events in a logical framework. The authors introduce a new logical operator called “Observation” to represent an event that can be partially observed.

The main contribution of the paper is the development of a logical framework for reasoning about partially observable events. The framework extends the standard modal logic with the new Observation operator, which allows for reasoning about events that are only partially observable.

The authors define a set of axioms and inference rules for the extended logic, and they show that the logic is sound and complete. They also present a number of examples to illustrate the use of the new operator in reasoning about partially observable events.

The paper is significant because it addresses an important issue in reasoning about complex systems, where the state of the system may not be fully observable. The authors’ logical framework provides a way to reason about such systems, even when the observations are incomplete or uncertain.

Overall, the paper presents a new approach to reasoning about partially observable events in a logical framework, which has significant implications for many fields, including artificial intelligence, robotics, and decision theory.

Vaishak Belle - I don’t think that paper exists

I apologize for the confusion. You are correct that the paper I referred to does not exist. I apologize for any confusion or inconvenience this may have caused.

If you have any other questions or would like me to provide information on a specific topic, please let me know.

Vaishak Belle - Explain the paper “Reasoning about noisy sensors and effectors in the situation calculus” by Bacchus et al.

The paper “Reasoning about noisy sensors and effectors in the situation calculus” by Bacchus et al. (2005) addresses the problem of how to reason about the effects of actions and observations in the presence of noise and uncertainty.

In many real-world applications, sensors and effectors are subject to various forms of noise, such as measurement errors or actuator faults. This can lead to uncertainty in the observed state of the world and the effects of actions. The paper proposes a framework for representing and reasoning about such uncertainties in the Situation Calculus.

⁸<https://medium.com/vaishakbelle/chatgpt-confabulates-wildly-about-the-probabilistic-situation-calculus-6cea41287f8d>

The authors introduce a new formalism called the Probabilistic Situation Calculus (PSC) that extends the Situation Calculus with probability theory. The PSC allows for reasoning about uncertain state transitions and observations in a unified way. Specifically, it allows for representing the probability distribution over the possible next states and observations given the current state and action.

The paper then presents a probabilistic variant of the Regression algorithm, which is a key algorithm for automated planning in the Situation Calculus. The authors show how the algorithm can be extended to handle uncertain observations and actions, and how it can be used to compute plans that are robust to sensor and effector noise.

Overall, the paper is significant because it presents a framework for representing and reasoning about uncertainty in the Situation Calculus, which has important implications for many applications in artificial intelligence, robotics, and decision making.

Vaishak Belle - where in the paper do they prove the regression result

In the paper “Reasoning about noisy sensors and effectors in the situation calculus” by Bacchus et al. (2005), the authors present a probabilistic variant of the Regression algorithm and show how it can be used to handle uncertain observations and actions.

The proof of the regression result for the probabilistic variant of the algorithm is presented in Section 5 of the paper. Specifically, in Section 5.2, the authors define the probabilistic regression operator, which computes the probability distribution over the possible next states given a current state and an action.

The authors then prove the regression result for the probabilistic variant of the algorithm in Theorem 3, which states that the probability of a fluent holding in the next state can be computed by integrating over all possible next states weighted by their probability, where the probability of each next state is given by the probabilistic regression operator.

The proof of Theorem 3 builds upon the proof of the regression result for the standard (non-probabilistic) Regression algorithm, which is presented in many textbooks and papers on automated planning and the Situation Calculus. The authors provide additional details and insights into the proof, highlighting the modifications and extensions required to handle uncertainty in observations and actions.

Overall, Section 5 of the paper provides a detailed exposition of the probabilistic variant of the Regression algorithm and the proof of the regression result for this algorithm.

The Bacchus et al paper is cited 216 times on google scholar, which I suppose makes it somewhat niche, so one might think its impressive that it has scrounged together some facts about this stuff from different sources, but on the one hand is plain irresponsible. Unless there are enough textual sources to document some topic, we should expect confabulated details.

6 Very dangerous

Since Hinton gave those noteworthy interviews, concerns about the the existential risk posed by AI technology are gaining prominence, implicitly assuming a conscious super-intelligent AI.⁹

Clearly, there is long-term risk involved with AI, as with any technology. Perhaps, there is more risk with AI, especially if we consider the assumed intellectual growth of such systems bordering on or potentially surpassing our intelligence. Vanilla LLMs may not get us there, and whether we want to get there is very questionable [23].

So, in the interim, let’s also acknowledge short-term risks. As Hinton [39] hints, the potential for bad actors to exploit chatbot technology for nefarious purposes is boundless. With the ability to learn

⁹<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2023/may/25/no-10-acknowledges-existential-risk-ai-first-time-rishi-sunak>

from GitHub code (a public repository for open-source computer code), these bad actors could leverage the technology to create tricky hacks and spread misinformation [32]. (Ironically, there is work on using language models to fight misinformation [71]).

Given the slow pace of action on issues like climate change, the idea of our society stepping up to address these concerns is sobering at best. Thus, I don't see this as an existential threat, in the sense of the 1990s Skynet system gone rogue, but rather a threat to our democracy and sanity. Such chatbots might spread misinformation by bots (whose code itself is provided by ChatGPT) deployed in the thousands, job loss (as enabled by, say, writing code or text, and physical systems such as self-driving cars and delivery drones), and the use of remote-operated weapons [24]. None of these necessarily require any notion of general-purpose intelligence: undergraduate statistics and control theory suffice. However, their impact on our lives will likely be profound.

And isn't it curious that companies like OpenAI, its partners and competitors, who have released their instances of chatbots into the wild without asking for our permission, and without any large-scale ethical review, are the ones begging for regulation? The similarity between Mark Zuckerberg pleading for regulation of social networks with the US Senate and this case is astounding and frankly, disturbing.

7 What's the way forward?

Putting aside the short-term and long-term risks posed by chatbot technology, a detailed discussion of which we defer to other experts [17], we feel there is still much to be said about frameworks that explicitly describe a specified behavior for agents [62, 9]. In our view, to design general-purpose AI with a behavior specification, we should turn to the notable work on integrating logic and learning using new representation languages that can express both qualitative and quantitative information.

Of course, it is very possible that some aspects of the qualitative and quantitative information could be extracted using large language models, as is already partly attempted in [65, 73]. With expert intervention and guidance, it is plausible to consider such models becoming a major way to collate formal knowledge. We will gloss over the promise of such strategies for now and simply report on the idea of representation languages that effectively combine qualitative, categorical, and quantitative aspects.

Statistical relational learning and neuro-symbolic AI are having a growing impact on recent discussions regarding the connection between (deep) learning and logical syntax [40, 51, 31, 10].¹⁰ These fields are motivated by the use of relations and logical reasoning, specifically entailment and satisfaction, in learning paradigms. They recognize that the world is inherently relational; objects have properties and attributes, employees have employers that are part of organisations, individuals are part of social networks. More elaborately, in biological networks, genes are the fundamental units of heredity that determine the traits of an organism. The process by which genes are expressed in proteins involves several steps, including transcription and translation, that are critical for the proper functioning of cells and organisms. If we need to reason about biological data, then algorithms that harness these relationships and processes are fundamental.

Logical reasoning is crucial to deduce properties about these relationships. For example, if we know that a dog is a mammal and a cat is a mammal, we should be able to deduce that they both give birth to live young, except unless those mammals that are monotremes. On the other hand, if we know that insects cannot be mammals, then we can also deduce that a dog cannot be an insect.

In the insular world of (deep) machine learning, where we assume that objects are atomic and independent, the incorporation of logical artifacts provides a much richer understanding of the world and its objects, leading to a more nuanced and accurate interpretation of the data.

¹⁰The material below is adapted from a recent book by the author [11], but has been extended to incorporate details and discussions about neuro-symbolic AI.

A second important area where the impact of symbols extends to is the notion of explainability in artificial intelligence. While traditionally this area has been about interpreting decision boundaries, it now includes attempts to use logical and programmatic objects to characterize the prediction model. See, for example, recent celebrated successes on deep concept induction [46, 34]. There is the more complex area of constructing mental models of the users and providing explanations relative to that putative user [42]. This area is also governed by symbolic and formal principles. Symbolic principles such as sufficiency and necessity are also being used to explore causal dimensions for explanations [26].

8 A first-order logical viewpoint

Despite this success and the many syntactic flavors explored in the research community, the underlying logical language is essentially propositional. Almost always, the outputs of the learning model (such as a neural network) are either interpreted probabilistically over a finite set of propositional variables, or as the numeric truth value accorded to a finite set of propositions (in fuzzy logical approaches). Even in a (probabilistic) logic programming setting such as ProbLog, cycle breaking strategies are considered to reduce query-driven reasoning to probabilistic labels over finitely many propositions via weighted model counting [64, 35].

In what follows, *our aim is to briefly survey and articulate the logical and philosophical foundations of using (first-order) logic to represent (probabilistic) knowledge in a non-technical fashion.* Our motivation is three fold. First, for machine learning researchers unaware of why the research community cares about relational representations, this article can serve as a gentle introduction. Second, for logical experts who are newcomers to the learning area, such an article can help in navigating the differences between finite vs infinite, and subjective probabilities vs random-world semantics. Finally, for researchers from statistical relational learning (StarAI) and neuro-symbolic AI (NeSyAI), who are usually embedded in finite worlds with subjective probabilities, appreciating what infinite domains and random-world semantics brings to the table is of utmost theoretical import: in fact, one may even argue it is needed to make the area well-defined! StarAI and NeSyAI wishes to generalize to unforeseen examples, and deal with statistical properties, and yet their prove properties for finite models and degrees of belief.

Of course, the use of a relational language (with a finite domain notwithstanding), that only serves as syntactic sugar for the specification for probabilistic models, is not without its advantages. It can greatly simplify the specification of relations and hierarchies over random variables, and can also speed up probabilistic inference in some cases by appealing to first-order resolution [67]. *But by incorporating probabilistic reasoning into first-order logic, we might be able to better deal with infinite domains and incomplete knowledge in a more principled way, and allowing for the specification of random properties (and not simply subjective probabilities, as assumed by current mainstream languages) in an open-world setting.* However, there will still challenges to be addressed, such as the computational complexity of reasoning with large knowledge bases and the need for effective methods of learning from data.

9 Why representation matters

It is worth reflecting on the nature of knowledge representation and how it affects modeling and learning. Regardless of whether we use a logical representation (such as a logic program), a probabilistic one (such as a Bayesian network), or a connectionist one (such as a neural network), our goal is to represent information and capture the knowledge of a robot or vision system. We want to understand how this representation produces interesting conclusions that determine what the robot knows and understands about the world.

While acquisition is undoubtedly important, for now, we are focusing on the language used for representing information. It is crucial to equip this language with tools for modeling and reasoning about the world. In a statement remarkably similar in spirit, Pearl writes [60]:

This is why you will find me emphasizing and reemphasizing notation, language, vocabulary and grammar. For example, I obsess over whether we can express a certain claim in a given language and whether one claim follows from others. My emphasis on language also comes from a deep conviction that language shapes our thoughts. You cannot answer a question that you cannot ask, and cannot ask a question that you have no words for.

Which language should we choose, and what should we represent? Turing machines are foundational structures for investigating the computable universe. They offer minimal, yet powerful read and write operations. However, being a computational abstraction means we have no means to concretely talk about what the robot knows about the environment it operates in. Likewise, binary system code runs robotic software, but is too coarse and opaque to explain a purposeful agent. Vectorized representations and non-linear decision boundaries as obtained by sigmoid neural units over many interconnected layers are also too coarse to explain the functioning of a deep network. Although these models seem capable of capturing a potentially infinite hypothesis space and high-dimensional data, including high-resolution images such as mammograms, an operational description is too opaque for humans to decipher.

Therefore, we require a modeling framework that is understandable to domain experts and allows for the updating and provision of new information, while also being suitable for computational processes. In particular, by a representation, we mean a mapping from one entity to another. The former is concrete and computationally processable. For example, “rain” might stand for the assertion that it is raining today. Reasoning is the computational processing of representations to produce new knowledge. We focus on formal (symbolic) logic, where all information is stored explicitly or implicitly using symbols.

The distinction between explicit and implicit knowledge is important: explicit knowledge is often the information that is directly modelled or provided by the domain expert. This could come in the form of rules, databases, knowledge bases, graphs, or any other structured data. Implicit knowledge is what is obtained from the explicit knowledge through one or more reasoning steps.

Reasoning can be understood in two ways. First, it can define the mathematical framework for obtaining explicit knowledge from implicit knowledge. In logic, we often provide a semantics and/or proof theory that determines when sentences are “entailed” from a knowledge base (a set of sentences). Second, reasoning can provide an implementation strategy for computing entailments: an algorithm that takes a knowledge base and a query as input and outputs whether the query is entailed. Standard platforms for designing such algorithms include theorem provers, model checkers, and satisfiability solvers.

10 Logic and probability: how did we get here?

Leibniz perhaps first suggested that thinking could be understood as symbol manipulation, but it was only with the results of Boole and Frege that an algebraic view of logic became possible. Symbolic logic was primarily used for studying the foundations of mathematics until the 19th century. David Hilbert’s program, Kurt Gödel’s seminal incompleteness theorem, and other such inquiries studied the arithmetic of natural numbers and what logically follows from that arithmetic. John McCarthy, among others, began to see first-order logic as a formalism for capturing commonsense and language only since the 1960s [54, 55, 58]. He suggested that the system’s knowledge could be represented in a formal language, and a general-purpose algorithm could then determine the necessary actions to solve the problem at hand. A major advantage of this approach is that the representation can be scrutinized and understood by external observers, allowing them to improve the system’s behavior by making statements to it.

Numerous such languages emerged in the years to follow, but first-order logic remained at the forefront as a general and powerful option. Unfortunately, one of the main arguments against a logical approach is the pervasive uncertainty present in almost every domain of interest. This uncertainty can manifest in various forms, such as measurement errors (e.g. readings from a thermometer), the absence of categorical assertions (e.g. smoking may be a factor for cancer, but cancer is not an absolute consequence for smokers), and the presence of numerous “latent” factors. These factors include causes that the modeler may not have taken into account, which question the legitimacy of the model.

Modeling uncertain worlds required a rigorous formulation, which has been achieved through probabilistic models, of course. Probabilistic models, obtained either by explicit specification or implicitly induced by modern machine learning methods such as deep learning, have supercharged the application of statistical methods in language understanding, vision, and data analysis more generally.

Despite the success of probabilistic models, we observe that they are essentially propositional, yet are deployed in an inherently relational world. That is, they easily make sense of “flat” data, where atomic events are treated as independent and identically distributed random variables. This realization has led to the design of probabilistic concept languages, culminating in the area of statistical relational learning, neuro-symbolic AI, and other hybrid languages.

Note that there is a considerable history on the unification of logic and probability, including early work by Carnap and Gaifman [22, 36]. Interested readers can refer to [10] for a discussion on the historical development.

11 First-order logic

First-order logic is, as discussed above, a widely studied formalism. To contrast it with popular proposals in statistical relational learning, let us start with an example often used in that community, which involves smoking within social networks. We will then discuss variations allowed by propositional and first-order logic, while also briefly demonstrating their features. As will become clear, virtually every formalism from that community does not support arbitrary first-order logic. There is one good reason for this: first-order logic is only semi-decidable, and computing entailments is not tractable [18]. (Although first-order logic with reals as its domain is decidable, it is best used to reason about arithmetic properties, as seen in satisfiability modulo solvers.)

Let us imagine two individuals a (for Alice) and b (for Bob) such that a is a smoker and the two are friends. Using $S(x)$ as a predicate to mean x is a smoker and $F(x, y)$ to mean x is a friend of y , we have: $S(a) \wedge F(a, b)$. There are two propositional assertions here, connected using a conjunction, to say both are true in the knowledge base (KB).

Suppose we found that smokers influence those in their social networks to also smoke, in which case, we would wish to add $S(b)$ to the KB. However, rather than working this out by hand, we might wish to express this observation using an implication rule: $S(a) \wedge F(a, b) \supset S(b)$. Such rules involve only constants, and so, with quantifiers, we will be able to say that the smokers rule applies to every individual: $\forall x, y. S(x) \wedge F(x, y) \supset S(y)$. The quantification is over a “domain of discourse”, which defines the constants to which the expression following the quantification applies.

Naturally, the knowledge base (KB) contains “facts”, i.e., ground atoms, such as $S(a)$ and $F(a, b)$, in addition to quantified formulas. These facts constitute explicit knowledge. By applying these facts to the rules, we can derive $S(b)$, which is implicit in the sense of the terminology used earlier. In this way, the truth value for every instance of $S(x)$ can be determined from explicit or implicit knowledge, similar to a database. This denotes the case of “complete knowledge.”

Incompleteness is usually expressed using disjunctions and existential quantifiers. For example, assuming a third constant c for Carol: $(S(a) \vee S(c)) \wedge \neg(S(a) \wedge S(c))$ says that either Alice or Carol is a smoker but not both.

The use of an existential statement can declare the existence of an individual with a certain property, but not specify who that individual might be. For example, the following sentence states that there is a friend of Alice who is not Carol: $(\exists x. F(x, b)) \wedge \neg F(c, b)$. Suppose we further stipulate that no one can be their own friend: $\forall x. \neg F(x, x)$. Of course, if our domain were finite and consisted only of the individuals discussed so far - $\{a, b, c\}$ - then $F(a, b)$ would follow from the above two sentences. However, if the domain is infinite, then infinitely many candidates are possible friends of Bob, but we are not certain of any one of them.

11.1 Infinite domains

In addition to incomplete information about domains, other types of incomplete knowledge can also be expressed with infinite domains. For instance, when quantifiers range over an infinite set, the sentence $\forall x. x \neq a \supset S(x)$ states that there are infinitely many individuals who are smokers, except for Alice who might or might not be a smoker. Therefore, it models unknown atoms. To represent unknown values, we can use the following sentence: $\forall x(S(x) \supset \text{eyecolor}(x) \neq \text{green})$, which declares that among smokers in our population, of whom there may be infinitely many, none has green eyes.

Although there are a wide range of formalisms in statistical relational learning, constants are typically fixed in advance and are finite. Functions are rarely allowed, and often the interpretation of predicates is fixed as well: that is, the set of ground atoms is fixed, as well as their truth values. When these formalisms allow atoms to be decorated with probabilities, there is some flexibility in terms of the interpretation of predicates, in the sense that a positive instance is more likely than a negative instance, or vice versa.

As noted, the full first-order language, especially over a possibly infinite domain, can allow for unknown sets of atoms, their possible values, and varying sets of objects (e.g., when the set of humans is left open). This makes standard first-order logic a powerful and general-purpose language for representing knowledge, and we believe it can be a promising candidate for the next generation of probabilistic relational models.

In fact, keeping the domain undefined is often referred to as “open-world” modelling. Note that closeness is not difficult to implement in open-world models, should we so wish. For example, the sentence below says that Alice and Bob are both smokers, and everyone else is not: $\forall x[(x = a \vee x = b) \supset S(x)] \wedge [(x \neq a \wedge x \neq b) \supset \neg S(x)]$.

11.2 Probabilities on formulas

The standard way to represent incomplete knowledge in symbolic logic is through the use of disjunctions and existential quantifiers. A logical disjunction expresses qualitative uncertainty, but does not commit to which of the disjuncts is more likely than the other.

For example, suppose we toss a coin and find that it lands on heads nine out of ten times. We might believe it is a loaded coin and ascribe a probability of 0.9 to observing heads on the next toss. Suppose we read three plausible reports, two of which suggest that Alice is not a smoker, but the third asserts that she is. We might ascribe a probability of $2/3$ to $S(a)$. However, given that a report about Alice being a smoker might have been more recent or that Alice accidentally admitted she occasionally smokes, we might treat it as a true but lesser-known fact and ignore the other reports. Whichever the case may be, we need a language to reason about the *degrees of belief* – i.e., subjective probabilities – of the agent.

One of the simplest and most widely studied approaches to dealing with degrees of belief in logic involves the concept of *possible worlds*, where each world represents a distinct interpretation of the underlying knowledge base. We ascribe a probability (or more generally, a weight) to each world. To determine the probability of a statement $S(a)$, we sum the probabilities of all worlds where $S(a)$ is true. We may also

use weights and consider the ratio of that sum to a *normalization factor*, which is simply the sum of the probabilities of all worlds.

11.3 Probabilities on atoms

Suppose $S(a)$ is believed with a probability of 1. What is the probability that Bob is also a smoker? Given that $S(a)$ is entailed by KB, meaning it holds in every possible model of the KB, we cannot infer anything about $S(b)$ without further information. The probability of $S(b)$ depends on the possible worlds. If $S(b)$ is also entailed by the KB, it would be accorded a probability of 1 as well. However, if some models of the KB did not satisfy $S(b)$, then the probability of $\neg S(b)$ can be obtained by summing the probabilities of all such worlds, say this is r . The probability of $S(b)$ would then be $(1 - r)$. If the worlds all have equal weights, and $S(b)$ is false in r out of n worlds, then the probability of $S(b)$ would be $(n - r)/n$. From a logical viewpoint, the extension of the predicate S is different in every world, and it so happens that a is in every such extension while b is only in some.

Suppose we were able to assign a probability of $4/5$ to Alice and Bob being smokers based on the deterministic rule mentioned above. This rule can be represented in the KB as $4/5: (S(a) \wedge F(a, b)) \supset S(b)$, indicating that in 4 out of 5 worlds, Alice influences her friend to smoke. If all worlds had equal weights, this would mean that Alice influences her friend to smoke in $4/5$ of those worlds.

To further understand the rule, let's consider two scenarios with different probabilities for Alice being a smoker. Assume $\{S(a), F(a, b)\}$ is believed with probability 1. The noisy rule states that $S(b)$ is true in four-fifths of the worlds, giving us a probability of $4/5$ for $S(b)$.

Now, let's assume $F(a, b)$ is believed with probability 1, but $S(a)$ only with a probability of $2/3$. Assuming equal weights to worlds for ease of explanation, $S(a)$ holds in two-thirds of the worlds, and in four-fifths of those worlds, the noisy rule requires that $S(b)$ holds. Therefore, the probability of $S(b)$ is $2/3 \times 4/5 = 8/15$.

Let's consider a simple example where a unique distribution would not arise. Suppose $\forall x, y(F(x, y))$ is believed with probability 1. This means that every individual is a friend of everybody else (including themselves). Now suppose $S(a) \vee S(c)$ is believed with probability 1. In this case, no specification is provided for the individual probabilities of $S(a)$ and $S(c)$. It is not acceptable to assign a probability of 0 to both $S(a)$ and $S(c)$. However, provided that this requirement is satisfied, there are many possibilities. Most statistical relational languages will either disallow such specifications or make assumptions about how the distribution should be defined for such disjunctions. Notable exceptions allowing for imprecise probabilities do exist, but they are often not in a first-order formalism. See [6, 13] for examples that involve first-order logic and multiple distributions.

Suppose we are interested in the probability of $S(b)$ given the noisy smokers rule above and a similar instance resulting from $S(c)$: $4/5: (S(c) \wedge F(c, b)) \supset S(b)$. It is not hard to see that the probability of $S(b)$ should be $4/5$. This is because every world should satisfy $S(a)$ or $S(c)$ or both. Due to the universal rule about everyone being friends, $F(a, c)$ and $F(b, c)$ both hold. Consequently, in four-fifths of the worlds (assuming equal weights for simplicity), the smokers rule would imply that $S(b)$ must hold. Therefore, its probability is also $4/5$.

Suppose we instead said $S(a) \vee S(c)$ with a probability of $1/5$. In one-fifth of the possible worlds, $S(a)$ or $S(c)$ or both would be true. In four-fifths of those worlds, the smokers rule would mean that $S(b)$ must be true as well. Therefore, the probability of $S(b)$ would be $4/5 \times 1/5 = 4/25$ assuming equal weights.

11.4 Probabilities on quantified formulas

The examples from the previous section could be expressed more succinctly with the following noisy

quantified rule: $4/5: \forall x, y(S(x) \wedge F(x, y) \supset S(y))$. This rule states that in four-fifths of the worlds (assuming equal weights to worlds), friends of smokers are smokers too.

Suppose we know for certain that Alice and Bob are friends, and we ascribe a probability of $2/3$ to the atom $S(a)$. Then, in two-thirds of the worlds, $S(a)$ holds. In four-fifths of these worlds, the universal rule, together with the certain knowledge that $F(a, b)$, means that $S(b)$ holds. The probability of $S(b)$ is then $2/3 \times 4/5 = 8/15$.

However, one might find it striking how the reading of this rule contrasts with the statistical observation that motivates it. Presumably, we would like to say that in 80% of the population, friends of smokers are also smokers. This is statistical information, of course, but the way the rule is written requires that the rule must hold in four-fifths of the worlds. In other words, if in every world there is some smoker whose friend is not a smoker, then the rule clearly holds in no world, and so its probability should be 0.

This is an early observation in the field of probabilistic logics [1, 3, 4, 38]. The possible-worlds model with probabilities over worlds is used to define degrees of belief, but it is not appropriate for statistical information. To represent statistical information, a different formal setup is required. This setup, called the *random-worlds* semantics, allows probabilities to be ascribed to domain elements. With this approach, we can reason about the probability of a randomly chosen person being a smoker, or the probability of two randomly chosen individuals being friends, and so on. This would be useful in cases where the smokers universal is known to not be true in the real world.

In most statistical relational and neuro-symbolic languages, the intended statistical interpretation is often ignored, resulting in noisy quantified rules. These rules are commonly interpreted using the possible-worlds model.

Likewise, probabilities on existentially quantified formulas are to be understood the same way. For example: $1/5: \exists x(S(x))$ says that in one-fifth of the worlds (assuming equal weights on worlds), there is someone who is a smoker. It is *not* saying that one out of five individuals is a smoker or that there is a 20% chance that a randomly chosen individual is a smoker.

Both of these topics require a random-worlds semantics, and integrating that with a possible-worlds semantics could be an exciting area of research for mainstream statistical relational and neuro-symbolic AI.

11.5 What lies beneath

ProbLog, probabilistic databases, Markov logic networks, Bayesian networks, factor graphs [61], and their neuro-symbolic extensions can be understood either in terms of a computational framework called *weighted model counting* [25, 64], or via a fuzzy semantics that accords non-binary truth values to atoms. Let us discuss them in turn.

Given a logical language with n propositions, and therefore, 2^n possible truth assignments (or worlds) $\mathcal{M} = \{M_1, \dots, M_{2^n}\}$, consider a weight function μ mapping literals to non-negative reals. By extension, let the weight of a world $\mu(M)$ be defined as the product of the weights of the literals that hold at M . Then the weighted model count of a propositional formula ϕ is defined as:

$$WMC(\phi) \doteq \sum_{\{M \in \mathcal{M}, M \models \phi\}} \mu(M) \Big/ \sum_{\{M \in \mathcal{M}\}} \mu(M).$$

A Bayesian network can be encoded as a propositional knowledge base, with the conditional dependencies expressed as implications [25, 64]. In Markov logic networks, propositions appearing in a clause correspond to the dependent random variables in an undirected graphical model. The probability function of the nodes can be further expressed in terms of a weight function of the above sort. In this case, the probability of some query q (a propositional formula) is obtained using:

$$WMC(KB \wedge q) \Big/ WMC(KB).$$

In other words, relative to the models of KB, we compute the weights of those worlds additionally satisfying q .

There are a few notable exceptions to picture in the statistical relational learning community; see [8] for more discussions. For example, in BLOG [57], function symbols are allowed in the language over an infinite domain, thus supporting open-world modeling. However, for computational reasons, various restrictions are placed both for the language and its implementation. Well-defined programs, for example, restrict the use of logical connectives. When computing probabilities, it avoids instantiating infinitely many terms by sampling values for function symbols. When it comes to termination, moreover, a number of structural conditions need to hold, including one that the quantifiers over formulas can only range over finite sets.

In a second approach to the semantics of neural learning in logic, binary truth is relaxed. In particular, because the outputs of neural networks are real-valued and need to be interpreted logically, there has been a recent revival of fuzzy logic in neuro-symbolic AI [16, 37, 47]. Fuzzy logic allows for degrees of truth, unlike classical logic which assumes a proposition is either true or false. In fuzzy logic, logical connectives are interpreted as maximum and product operators, where the maximum operator corresponds to disjunction and the product operator corresponds to conjunction.

When the inputs to these operators are either 0 or 1, it can be seen that maximum and product collapses to the classical interpretation. However, when the inputs are reals between 0 and 1, formulas are evaluated to values that do not correspond to being strictly true or false. This makes the semantics of complex formulas hard to interpret. Although there is some research on first-order fuzzy logic over non-finite domains, much of the work on neuro-symbolic AI is limited to finite domains [37].

A common argument in favor of fuzzy logic is that it may be more feasible computationally [68, 69], although this comes at the cost of a hard-to-interpret semantics. However, recent discussions have raised the point that neural networks are trained for conditional probabilities, making it reasonable to interpret the output in a probabilistic manner [68, 69]. As a result, it may be more appropriate to consider using probabilistic (logical) languages. Striking a balance between ease of computation and interpretability of semantics is crucial, and perhaps the final decision may depend on the specific application.

12 What about the complexity of reasoning?

In the above sections, we discussed the importance of reasoning using the friends-smokers example. We also explored the advantages of first-order logic in terms of the expressiveness it offers for open-world scenarios. However, we did not delve into the strategies that allow us to reason in a decidable way with fragments of first-order logic. Fortunately, there are numerous methods available to tackle this issue, and we shall mention them in brief.

As is well known, areas such as descriptive complexity and finite model theory demonstrate that logic could serve as an abstraction for understanding computation vis-à-vis representation. It is also well-known that there is a trade-off between the expressiveness of the language and the tractability of the reasoning task.

On the one hand it is widely acknowledged that relations and more generally, the expressiveness of first-order logic is extremely useful for capturing language and concepts required for common-sense reasoning. This explains the use of first-order logic in database theory, statistical relational learning, automated planning, knowledge representation (e.g., description logics, and reasoning about actions) and verification. But at the same time the entailment problem is only semi-decidable.

Since Goedel's celebrated results on the intractability of logic, there has been a wide range of approaches to deal with this trade-off especially in the knowledge representation, symbolic computation and the statistical relational learning communities. They can be broadly classified into three categories. The easiest ap-

proach is to simply restrict the language to propositional logic. Popular frameworks in statistical relational learning such as Markov logic networks and relational Bayesian networks as well as relational probabilistic planning languages take this approach [28, 43, 50, 72].

A second approach is to limit the expressiveness of the language in terms of the size of the predicates (but not necessarily in terms of the size of the domain). Description logics are popular concept representation languages in knowledge representation that only allow predicates with utmost two arguments. When the domain is further assumed to be finite, certain other computational tasks beyond entailment turn out to be tractable [20, 44].

A third approach, stemming from the knowledge representation community but less popular in other communities, is to limit reasoning. Here, the entailment relation itself is weakened by way of introducing non-traditional semantics [49]. However, because the semantical apparatus is often complicated, they have understandably not been pursued by or used in other communities.

Somewhere in between the three approaches, there is also the well-known Horn clause restriction, seen most prominently in logic programming and its derivatives. It potentially allows for an infinite Herbrand universe, but the grounding of the program is only performed against a ground query, which permits a propositional encoding sometimes [35]. This enables the use of logic programming in a wide variety of applications, including statistical relational learning by decorating clauses further with probabilities. But most common flavors are limited in only allowing one positive literal in a clause, and is non-monotonic.

A fourth approach is to exploit symmetries in first-order representations. For example, the area of lifted reasoning avoids grounding a probabilistic relational model by appealing to first-order resolution [67]. In somewhat a similar spirit, a recent result shows that there is an intuitive fragment of first-order disjunctive knowledge, for which reasoning is decidable and can be reduced to propositional satisfiability [12]. Knowledge bases in this fragment essentially amounts to universally quantified first-order clauses, but without arity restrictions and without restrictions on the appearance of negation. Queries, however, are expected to be ground formulas. They achieve this result is by showing how the entailment over infinitely many infinite-sized structures can be reduced to a search over finitely many finite-size structures. The crux of the argument lies in showing that names not mentioned in the knowledge base and the query behave identically (in a suitable formal sense).

Overall, if we are extend the statistical relational and neuro-symbolic formalisms to full first-order expressiveness, some of these strategies need to be combined and extended carefully, and this is an exciting area for future research.

13 Wrapping up

We began this paper by investigating the claims of the cleverness and existential threat of large language models. Although it is impossible at this stage to predict what future architectures and innovations with these models will look like, it seems fairly clear that the current way of associative learning is not strong enough to demonstrate general-purpose intelligence, at least from a logical reasoning point of view. In the latter part of the article, we then focused on existing areas that combine probabilistic reasoning and qualitative and logical representations, as represented by statistical relational learning and neuro-symbolic AI. These areas are promising and can certainly be integrated with the outputs of large language models, as already attempted by many in the areas of knowledge base completion and knowledge acquisition from textual and unstructured data. However, from a first-order logical viewpoint, there still remains some deeper foundational work that is needed. Consequently, there are exciting future avenues to explore here that should provide interesting topics for PhD students of logic.

References

- [1] M. Abadi and J. Halpern. Decidability and expressiveness for first-order logics of probability. *Information and Computation*, 112(1):1 – 36, 1994.
- [2] R. Azamfirei, S. R. Kudchadkar, and J. Fackler. Large language models and the perils of their hallucinations. *Critical Care*, 27(1):1–2, 2023.
- [3] F. Bacchus, A. Grove, J. Y. Halpern, and D. Koller. Forming beliefs about a changing world. In *Proc. AAAI*, pages 222–229, 1994.
- [4] F. Bacchus, A. J. Grove, J. Y. Halpern, and D. Koller. From statistical knowledge bases to degrees of belief. *Artificial intelligence*, 87(1-2):75–143, 1996.
- [5] F. Bacchus, J. Y. Halpern, and H. J. Levesque. Reasoning about noisy sensors and effectors in the situation calculus. *Artificial Intelligence*, 111(1–2):171 – 208, 1999.
- [6] F. Bacchus, J. Y. Halpern, and H. J. Levesque. Reasoning about noisy sensors and effectors in the situation calculus. *Artificial Intelligence*, 111(1–2):171 – 208, 1999.
- [7] M. Banko, M. J. Cafarella, S. Soderland, M. Broadhead, and O. Etzioni. Open information extraction from the web. In *IJCAI*, volume 7, pages 2670–2676, 2007.
- [8] V. Belle. Open-universe weighted model counting. In *AAAI*, 2017.
- [9] V. Belle. Logic meets learning: From aristotle to neural networks. In *Neuro-Symbolic Artificial Intelligence: The State of the Art*, pages 78–102. IOS Press, 2021.
- [10] V. Belle. Logic meets learning: From aristotle to neural networks. In *Neuro-Symbolic Artificial Intelligence: The State of the Art*, pages 78–102. IOS Press, 2021.
- [11] V. Belle. Toward robots that reason: Logic, probability & causal laws. 2023.
- [12] V. Belle and B. Juba. Implicitly learning to reason in first-order logic. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 32, 2019.
- [13] V. Belle and G. Lakemeyer. Reasoning about probabilities in unbounded first-order dynamical domains. In *IJCAI*, 2017.
- [14] V. Belle and H. J. Levesque. Reasoning about probabilities in dynamic systems using goal regression. In *Proc. UAI*, 2013.
- [15] V. Belle and I. Papantonis. Principles and practice of explainable machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.11698*, 2020.
- [16] T. R. Besold, A. d. Garcez, S. Bader, H. Bowman, P. Domingos, P. Hitzler, K.-U. Kühnberger, L. C. Lamb, D. Lowd, P. M. V. Lima, et al. Neural-symbolic learning and reasoning: A survey and interpretation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.03902*, 2017.
- [17] A. Birhane, A. Kasirzadeh, D. Leslie, and S. Wachter. Science in the age of large language models. *Nature Reviews Physics*, pages 1–4, 2023.

- [18] E. Boerger, E. Grädel, and Y. Gurevich. *The classical decision problem*. Springer Verlag, 1997.
- [19] R. J. Brachman and H. J. Levesque. *Machines like us: toward AI with common sense*. MIT Press, 2022.
- [20] D. Calvanese, G. De Giacomo, D. Lembo, M. Lenzerini, and R. Rosati. Data complexity of query answering in description logics. *Artificial Intelligence*, 195:335–360, 2013.
- [21] N. Carlini, F. Tramer, E. Wallace, M. Jagielski, A. Herbert-Voss, K. Lee, A. Roberts, T. B. Brown, D. Song, U. Erlingsson, et al. Extracting training data from large language models. In *USENIX Security Symposium*, volume 6, 2021.
- [22] R. Carnap. *Logical foundations of probability*. Routledge and Kegan Paul London, 1951.
- [23] D. J. Chalmers. Could a large language model be conscious? *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.07103*, 2023.
- [24] R. Chatila, V. Dignum, M. Fisher, F. Giannotti, K. Morik, S. Russell, and K. Yeung. Trustworthy ai. *Reflections on Artificial Intelligence for Humanity*, pages 13–39, 2021.
- [25] M. Chavira and A. Darwiche. On probabilistic inference by weighted model counting. *Artif. Intell.*, 172(6-7):772–799, 2008.
- [26] H. Chockler, D. Kroening, and Y. Sun. Explanations for occluded images. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 1234–1243, 2021.
- [27] R. Confalonieri, T. Weyde, T. R. Besold, and F. M. del Prado Martín. Using ontologies to enhance human understandability of global post-hoc explanations of black-box models. *Artificial Intelligence*, 296:103471, 2021.
- [28] J. Corander, T. Janhunen, J. Rintanen, H. J. Nyman, and J. Pensar. Learning chordal markov networks by constraint satisfaction. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 26: 27th Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2013. Proceedings of a meeting held December 5-8, 2013, Lake Tahoe, Nevada, United States.*, pages 1349–1357, 2013.
- [29] F. G. Cozman and H. N. Munhoz. Some thoughts on knowledge-enhanced machine learning. *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*, 2021.
- [30] A. Creswell, M. Shanahan, and I. Higgins. Selection-inference: Exploiting large language models for interpretable logical reasoning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.09712*, 2022.
- [31] A. d’Avila Garcez and L. C. Lamb. Neurosymbolic ai: The 3rd wave. *arXiv e-prints*, pages arXiv–2012, 2020.
- [32] L. De Angelis, F. Baglivo, G. Arzilli, G. P. Privitera, P. Ferragina, A. E. Tozzi, and C. Rizzo. Chatgpt and the rise of large language models: the new ai-driven infodemic threat in public health. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11:1567, 2023.
- [33] X. Dong, E. Gabrilovich, G. Heitz, W. Horn, N. Lao, K. Murphy, T. Strohmann, S. Sun, and W. Zhang. Knowledge vault: A web-scale approach to probabilistic knowledge fusion. In *Knowledge discovery and data mining*, 2014.

- [34] K. Ellis, A. Solar-Lezama, and J. Tenenbaum. Sampling for bayesian program learning. In *NIPS*, pages 1289–1297, 2016.
- [35] D. Fierens, G. V. den Broeck, I. Thon, B. Gutmann, and L. D. Raedt. Inference in probabilistic logic programs using weighted CNF’s. In *UAI*, pages 211–220, 2011.
- [36] H. Gaifman. Concerning measures in first order calculi. *Israel Journal of Mathematics*, 2(1):1–18, 1964.
- [37] A. S. d. Garcez, K. Broda, D. M. Gabbay, et al. *Neural-symbolic learning systems: foundations and applications*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2002.
- [38] J. Y. Halpern. *Reasoning about Uncertainty*. MIT Press, 2003.
- [39] W. Heaven. Geoffrey hinton tells us why he is now scared of the tech he helped build. *MIT Technology Review*, 2023.
- [40] P. Hitzler. Neuro-symbolic artificial intelligence: The state of the art. 2022.
- [41] M. Jang and T. Lukasiewicz. Consistency analysis of chatgpt. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.06273*, 2023.
- [42] S. Kambhampati. Challenges of human-aware ai systems. *AI Magazine*, 41(3), 2020.
- [43] S. Kok and P. Domingos. Learning markov logic networks using structural motifs. In *ICML*, pages 551–558, 2010.
- [44] D. Koller, A. Levy, and A. Pfeffer. P-classic: a tractable probablistic description logic. In *Proc. AAAI / IAAI*, pages 390–397, 1997.
- [45] A. Kothari. Chatgpt, large language models, and generative ai as future augments of surgical cancer care. *Annals of Surgical Oncology*, pages 1–3, 2023.
- [46] B. M. Lake, R. Salakhutdinov, and J. B. Tenenbaum. Human-level concept learning through probabilistic program induction. *Science*, 350(6266):1332–1338, 2015.
- [47] L. C. Lamb, A. Garcez, M. Gori, M. Prates, P. Avelar, and M. Vardi. Graph neural networks meet neural-symbolic computing: A survey and perspective. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.00330*, 2020.
- [48] Y. Liu, G. Lakemeyer, and H. J. Levesque. A logic of limited belief for reasoning with disjunctive information. In *KR*, pages 587–597, 2004.
- [49] Y. Liu and H. J. Levesque. Tractable reasoning in first-order knowledge bases with disjunctive information. In *Proc. AAAI*, pages 639–644, 2005.
- [50] D. Lowd and A. Rooshenas. Learning markov networks with arithmetic circuits. In *AISTATS*, 2013.
- [51] R. Manhaeve, S. Dumancic, A. Kimmig, T. Demeester, and L. De Raedt. Deepproblog: Neural probabilistic logic programming. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 31, 2018.
- [52] G. F. Marcus. *The algebraic mind: Integrating connectionism and cognitive science*. MIT press, 2003.
- [53] P. Mateus, A. Pacheco, J. Pinto, A. Sernadas, and C. Sernadas. Probabilistic situation calculus. *Annals of Math. and Artif. Intell.*, 32(1-4):393–431, 2001.

- [54] J. McCarthy. Programs with common sense. In *Semantic Information Processing*, pages 403–418. MIT Press, 1968.
- [55] J. McCarthy. Situations, Actions and Causal Laws. Technical report, Stanford University, 1963. Also in M. Minsky (ed.), *Semantic Information Processing*, MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 1968.
- [56] S. A. McIlraith, T. Son, and H. Zeng. Semantic web services. *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, 16(2):46–53, 2001.
- [57] B. Milch, B. Marthi, S. J. Russell, D. Sontag, D. L. Ong, and A. Kolobov. BLOG: Probabilistic models with unknown objects. In *Proc. IJCAI*, pages 1352–1359, 2005.
- [58] L. Morgenstern and S. A. McIlraith. John McCarthy’s legacy. *Artificial Intelligence*, 175(1):1 – 24, 2011.
- [59] F. Niu, C. Zhang, C. Ré, and J. W. Shavlik. Deepdive: Web-scale knowledge-base construction using statistical learning and inference. *VLDS*, 12:25–28, 2012.
- [60] J. Pearl and D. Mackenzie. *The book of why*.
- [61] L. D. Raedt, K. Kersting, S. Natarajan, and D. Poole. Statistical relational artificial intelligence: Logic, probability, and computation. *Synthesis Lectures on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning*, 10(2):1–189, 2016.
- [62] R. Reiter. *Knowledge in action: logical foundations for specifying and implementing dynamical systems*. MIT Press, 2001.
- [63] C. Rudin. Stop explaining black box machine learning models for high stakes decisions and use interpretable models instead. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 1(5):206–215, 2019.
- [64] T. Sang, P. Beame, and H. A. Kautz. Performing bayesian inference by weighted model counting. In *AAAI*, pages 475–482, 2005.
- [65] D. Sileo and A. Lerno. Mindgames: Targeting theory of mind in large language models with dynamic epistemic modal logic. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.03353*, 2023.
- [66] J. Šlapeta. Are chatgpt and other pretrained language models good parasitologists? *Trends in Parasitology*, 2023.
- [67] G. Van den Broeck. *Lifted Inference and Learning in Statistical Relational Models*. PhD thesis, KU Leuven, 2013.
- [68] E. van Krieken, E. Acar, and F. van Harmelen. Analyzing differentiable fuzzy implications. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.03472*, 2020.
- [69] E. van Krieken, E. Acar, and F. van Harmelen. Analyzing differentiable fuzzy logic operators. *Artificial Intelligence*, 302:103602, 2022.
- [70] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, Ł. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin. Attention is all you need. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 30, 2017.

- [71] C. Whitehouse, T. Weyde, P. Madhyastha, and N. Komninos. Evaluation of fake news detection with knowledge-enhanced language models. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*, volume 16, pages 1425–1429, 2022.
- [72] H. Younes and M. Littman. PPDDL 1. 0: An extension to pddl for expressing planning domains with probabilistic effects. Technical report, Carnegie Mellon University, 2004.
- [73] H. Zhang, J. Huang, Z. Li, M. Naik, and E. Xing. Improved logical reasoning of language models via differentiable symbolic programming. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.03742*, 2023.
- [74] K. Zhou, D. Jurafsky, and T. Hashimoto. Navigating the grey area: Expressions of overconfidence and uncertainty in language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2302.13439*, 2023.